

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D8.4 Guidelines and recommendations for public health summary report

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Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project examined how vulnerability is defined and addressed in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The project drew upon complex adaptive system and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications, as well as resident perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation. The current deliverable D8.4 aims to give an overview of the key lessons learnt and recommendations for public health responses. It draws on the work conducted in WP5 that analysed COVID-19's impact and response from a public health perspective, with a specific focus on health inequality and vulnerability.

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Introduction

The COVINFORM project examined how vulnerability is defined and addressed in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The project drew upon complex adaptive system and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications, as well as resident perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation.

The current deliverable D8.4 falls under the scope of WP8 that focuses on the development of solutions, guidelines, and recommendations, and aims to give an overview of the key lessons learnt and recommendations for public health responses. It draws on the work conducted in WP5 that analysed COVID-19's impact and response from a public health perspective, with a specific focus on health inequality and vulnerability. This work involved both desk-research as well as empirical research with public health workers and decision-makers, and resulted in a number of reports that provide in-depth analyses and discussions about public health responses in the context of COVID-19.

Table 1. Overview of the deliverables on public health written in the context of WP5¹

Number	Date	Title	Topics covered	Authors
D5.1	June 2021	Baseline Report: Public health responses	Explores public health responses to the COVID-19 pandemic across COVINFORM partner countries	Jil Molenaar, Lore Van Praag & Akim Aalou (UANTWERPEN)
D5.2	October 2021	Research Design: Public health responses	Outlines research design of the empirical research activities for WP5	Jil Molenaar & Lore Van Praag (UANTWERPEN)
D5.3	March 2022	Analysis: Public health responses and impact	Examines public health responses to the COVID-19 pandemic in various dimensions: health vulnerabilities; the institutional, legal, and data collection factors influencing public health responses; communication around vaccines and vaccination campaigns; and the impacts of COVID-19 on healthcare workers.	Elena Ambrosetti & Marta Pasqualini (SAPIENZA); Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin & Louise Condon(SU); Diego Castellanos (URJC); Gloria Anderson & Massimo Fantoni (UCSC) Contributors: Itamar Laist & Chaim Rafalowsky (MDA); Jil Molenaar (UANTWERPEN)
D5.4	May 2022	Synthesis and lessons learnt on public health responses and impacts	Outlines findings of the expert interviews conducted with health care workers and public health policy- and decision makers.	Jil Molenaar, Hannah Robinson & Lore Van Praag (UANTWERPEN)

¹ The deliverables can be consulted on the project website: <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/>

D5.5	September 2022	Baseline Report: Public Health Responses – update M23	Provides cross-country synthesis of pandemic preparedness plans and evaluations of specific COVID-19 public health responses across COVINFORM partner-countries	Jil Molenaar (UANTWERPEN)
D5.6	February 2023	Research Design: Public Health Responses – update M28	Provides a short update of the research design for WP5 (D5.2), including a methodological reflection	Rut Van Caudenberg, Hannah Robinson & Lore Van Praag (UANTWERPEN)
D5.7	July 2023	Analysis: Public health responses and impact – update M33	Provides an overview of how the pandemic was managed in terms of public health responses, including changes over time and lessons learned in ten COVINFORM-partner countries.	Rut Van Caudenberg, Hannah Robinson & Lore Van Praag (UANTWERPEN); Chaim Rafalowski and Itamar Laist (MDA)
D5.8	September 2023	Synthesis and lessons learnt on public health responses and impact – update M35	Synthesizes and compares COVID-19 public health responses across ten COVINFORM partner-countries	Hannah Robinson, Rut Van Caudenberg & Lore Van Praag (UANTWERPEN)

Table 2: Overview of the external outputs relating to the context of WP5

Type	Title	Date	Summary
White Paper	Public Health Responses During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Lessons Learned and Recommendations for Policymakers	09/2023	Provides an overview of the multifaceted impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare systems and responses across ten case study countries, including lessons learned and recommendations.
Policy Brief	Community Mental Health Responses for Migrants During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Antwerp	09/2023	Provides an assessment of how community organisations have responded to mental health needs during the pandemic, based on academic paper.
Policy Brief	Micro-Politics of Agency Taken by Residents in Antwerp Due to COVID-19	09/2023	Explores how migrant micro-politics took place within a context of spatial inequalities during the pandemic, based on article.
Bi-Monthly Report	Using an Intersectional Lens to Understand the Unequal Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic	2021	This bi-monthly report uses an intersectional lens to understand the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.
Blog post	Has COVID-19 Changed Our Cities? Urban Planning Following the Pandemic	2022	This blogpost explores the impact of COVID-19 on urban planning.

Blog post	How COVID-19 Has Exposed Housing Inequalities: Insights from Antwerp	2022	This blogpost assesses how housing inequalities were exacerbated as a result of the pandemic, based on interviews from Antwerpen.
Blog post	How Vulnerable Groups Were Left Behind in Pandemic Response	07/06/2021	This blog post looks at vulnerability and how this was exacerbated.
Journal article	Migrants as 'Vulnerable Groups' in the COVID-19 Pandemic	12/22	This article unpicks the concept of vulnerability throughout the pandemic.
Journal article	A Beacon of Hope: A Qualitative Study on Migrants' Mental Health Needs and Community-Based Organizations' Responses During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Antwerp, Belgium	In review	Provides an assessment of how community organisations have responded to mental health needs during the pandemic.
Journal article	Feeling Stuck: The Micro-Politics of Migrant Dwelling Practices During COVID-19 in Antwerp	In review	Explores how migrant micro-politics took place within a context of spatial inequalities during the pandemic.

In this deliverable, we highlight four key takeaways from the COVINFORM project when it comes to public health responses: i) the importance of pandemic preparedness and adaptability of responses, ii) the need for a comprehensive understanding of vulnerabilities, iii) the need for enhanced data sharing and analysis, and iv) the impact of a health crisis on healthcare workers. In what follows, we present a short discussion of each of those themes. Based on promising practices and lessons learnt that were identified over the course of the project, we also include a list of recommendations that can serve as an inspiration in the face of future pandemics or other health crises.

1. Pandemic preparedness and adaptability

The COVID-19 public health responses varied significantly across the countries, shaping a diverse landscape of success, challenges, and adaptive strategies. One challenge faced by many countries in adapting to the evolving situation was the lack of a national pandemic plan. Often the only preparedness plans which countries had were outdated influenza plans, which limited the response. Other structural factors prevented countries from adapting easily to the pandemic, including complex government structures and unclear divisions of responsibilities.

The following recommendations aim to address the challenges observed during the COVID-19 pandemic and lay the foundation for more adaptive, efficient, and coordinated responses in the face of future health crises.

Recommendations

- Develop and maintain up-to-date national pandemic plans distinct from influenza plans to ensure preparedness for diverse health crises.
- Simplify complex government structures to enhance crisis management efficiency. Clarify and streamline the division of responsibilities between federal, regional, and local levels including establishing effective coordination mechanisms between the central government and autonomous regions.
- Foster co-governance arrangements to promote collaboration, even in politically tense situations. For example, develop uniform and effective communication strategies across the entire country and improve communication between different levels of decision-makers to ensure a coherent response.
- Promote transparent governance practices to build public trust and implement clear and accountable decision-making processes, particularly during crises.
- Foster effective collaboration between government levels and scientific communities to base decisions on technical-scientific evidence.
- Enhance multilevel structures to facilitate cooperation and coordination between different healthcare facilities and agencies.

2. Different dimensions of vulnerabilities

Vulnerability encompasses various dimensions, including physical health status, susceptibility to severe COVID-19 illness or health system disruptions, and social vulnerability tied to societal disparities like occupation, deprivation, family circumstances, legal status, and ethnicity. Additionally, vulnerability may arise from communication-related issues, where socio-structural, individual-level, and situational factors hinder access, comprehension, and response to COVID-19 communication. The global response to the pandemic witnessed evolving priorities in addressing vulnerability. Many countries initially emphasized physical vulnerability, with increasing focus on social vulnerability as the pandemic progressed.

Early measures prioritized reducing loss of life but were hindered by delays in lockdowns and inadequate preparedness, leaving vulnerable groups insufficiently protected. The pandemic also laid bare weaknesses in healthcare systems, often characterized by a lack of resources. Socio-economic vulnerabilities, linked to class, gender, and ethnicity, worsened due to crowded living conditions and overrepresentation in essential professions. Vulnerable populations, including the elderly and marginalized communities, faced elevated risks due to healthcare access disparities. Disruptions in non-COVID healthcare services exacerbated structural inequalities, limiting access to necessary medical care. Furthermore, the economic fallout of the pandemic exacerbated vulnerabilities across society.

The following recommendations aim to enhance the preparedness and response to health crises by addressing vulnerabilities comprehensively and ensuring equitable access to healthcare and resources for all citizens, with a particular focus on vulnerable groups.

Recommendations

- Explicitly consider various dimensions of vulnerability, including mental and physical health, social inequities, and communication-related factors, in pandemic planning and response.
- Explicitly include social determinants of health in pandemic plans, recognizing the interconnectedness of health and non-health vulnerabilities.
- Develop targeted interventions and inclusive policies to address the specific needs of vulnerable populations, including the elderly, people with disabilities, immigrants, and marginalised communities.
- Adapt communication strategies to engage with local contexts and accommodate diverse populations, ensuring that information reaches and is understood by vulnerable groups.
- Implement consistent data collection practices that take into account socio-economic factors to better understand and address vulnerabilities.
- Comprehensively address socio-economic inequalities to ensure equitable access to healthcare, resources, and support. Invest in robust social services and infrastructure to support vulnerable individuals and communities during crises.
- Adopt a holistic approach to addressing structural health inequalities, considering changing dimensions of vulnerability during a crisis.
- Involve local leaders and communities in crisis response efforts, particularly when reaching non-native speakers, to enhance community engagement.

3. Data management and coordination

The impact of data collection factors was analysed by considering the necessity for ongoing systematic collection, analysis and interpretation of data to guide the planning and implementation of public health measures and interventions. Furthermore, the challenges related to underreporting, temporal delays and data disaggregation in the COVID-19 pandemic were analysed. During the pandemic, the tension between data protection and health protection underscored the complexity of addressing vulnerabilities. Health data is identified as a special form of data and is therefore not easily accessible for public health institutions. Because of this reason, it was often not simple to identify health

vulnerabilities. Enhanced data sharing and analysis have the potential to bolster response strategies, catering to diverse population segments. Thus, the predicament of striking a balance between data protection and public health came to the forefront, raising concerns about safeguarding both data and health. The following recommendations take this into account.

Recommendations

- Conduct operational research to inform and guide decision making.
- Make data available to researchers, who can use it to steer decision making and cater to diverse population segments.
- Develop transparent communication strategies with regards to the release of detailed data.
- Address data protection concerns and misinformation to maintain public trust.
- Develop consistent and comparable data collection strategies to help with COVID-19 testing and vaccination criteria.

4. Health care system and workers

The COVID-19 pandemic has had profound impacts on healthcare workers. They faced increased workloads, longer working hours, and increased risks of exposure to the virus. Moreover, they experienced physical and emotional stress, were confronted with shortages of personal protective equipment and faced challenges in managing COVID-19 patients. Burnout, mental health issues, and financial problems were prevalent among healthcare workers, highlighting the strain they faced during the pandemic. Despite the unique aspects of how healthcare workers were affected in different countries, the shared experiences of healthcare workers across countries reflect the global impact of the pandemic on their well-being. Furthermore, despite their resilience and dedication, the inadequacy of support systems and resources, compounded by existing structural underfunding and staffing issues, intensified the crisis faced by healthcare workers. The following recommendations aim to address these issues.

Recommendations

- Provide comprehensive and adaptable support systems for healthcare workers, including mental health resources and leadership support.
- Ensure equitable pay and recognition for healthcare workers.
- Explore the use of Community Health Workers and practices.
- Ensure access to adequate personal protective equipment, strengthening healthcare-associated infection control in institutions, and developing inclusive strategies for healthcare delivery.
- Increase value placed on the social care sector, and prioritise funding of care within society.
- Ensure these factors are addressed within pandemic preparedness plans.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented unprecedented challenges to healthcare systems and responses across the world. In this deliverable, we highlighted some important takeaway messages from our analyses of COVID-19's impact and response from a public health perspective, with a specific focus on health inequality and vulnerability. It provides an overview of the impact of COVID-19 on various dimensions of public health responses and offers a list of recommendations that can serve as an inspiration in the face of future pandemics or other health crises. Encouraging practices such as targeted interventions, inclusive policies, systematic data collection, and recognition of socio-economic factors highlight the importance of developing comprehensive public health responses and addressing key factors which have influenced national and subnational responses. Furthermore, strengthening social services and enhancing coordination between government levels and healthcare providers are invaluable lessons that should guide future pandemic preparedness and response strategies to guarantee equitable care for all segments of society. Indeed, the critical nature of comprehending governance structures related to health and well-being, including considerations like centralization versus decentralisation, autonomy levels, communication frameworks, and preparedness for pandemics as well as legal factors play a pivotal role in understanding the implementation of public health responses and their impact.

To conclude, a key takeaway message is that public health responses need to be tailored to encompass the entire population, with a specific focus on addressing the unique needs of vulnerable groups within society. It has become clear that the COVID-19 crisis reinforced and widened pre-existing vulnerabilities and disadvantage relating to gender, age, socio-economic status and ethnicity/race and migration. Although the pandemic revealed useful insights into specific promising practices and targeted lessons learnt, it highlighted that structural changes are needed to address systemic socio-economic inequalities and vulnerabilities in society. These inequalities were already present prior to the pandemic, but have been further accentuated by its impact. In other words, to tackle vulnerabilities and health disparities in times of crisis, policies should address the social and economic factors that create and perpetuate them.